

Google Geo Apps for Creative Language Learning

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Google Maps

Definition

A product by Google that helps people to find location/position, plan a route, get reviews/ratings, and get visual impression.

Platforms

- Web app
- Mobile (Android & iOS)

Usage in Language Learning

Speaking

Ss practise giving directions using GMaps.

Example

T asks a S to give direction of they route he/she takes when commuting from his/her campus/school to LB LIA Margonda. S uses direction feature on GMaps.

Ss practise showing location using GMaps.

Example

T asks a S to show location of particular places on GMaps. T chooses a particular region on GMaps and selects several spots for practice material. Then, T asks ss to practise showing location with prepositions that they have learned.

Writing

Ss practise writing skill by writing a review of a place that they like to visit. The review should be written in multiple paragraphs in limited word count.

Example

Ss write a review about their favorite restaurant in Google Map. First, they rate the restaurant from 1 to 4 stars and they make a review about the place. In addition, Ss add photos for the place that they have reviewed.

T check Ss review for grammatical form, punctuation usage, spelling, etc.

Class Competition

GMaps give Google Local Guide title to anyone who actively contributes information about places that are listed in GMaps. There are point reward for contribution in categories, such as:

1. Rating: +1 point
2. Answer: +1 point
3. Respond to Q & As: +3 point
4. Review: +5 points
5. Photo: +5 points
6. Video: +7 points
7. Adding place: +15 points

Every time a GMaps user contribute information, he or she will get points and the points will accumulate as the user keep on contributing information. In return, Google will increase the level of Google Local Guide from 1 to infinite.

Example

T creates a class competition.

- A race to get to be the first to get Google Local Guide badge.
- A race to get to be the first to get Google Local Guide badge Level 2–5
- A race to contribute the most reviews and photos.

Google Streetview

Definition

A product by Google that helps people to take a virtual trip around important places in the world. Besides doing virtual trip, people can use Google Streetview app (mobile) to take 360 photo and upload it to Google Map or Facebook, for free.

Platforms

- Web app
- Mobile (Android & iOS)

Usage in Language Learning

Speaking 1

Ss do presentation in group or individually about a place in Streetview app (desktop or mobile). The presentation takes form in a virtual tour around a place using Streetview app.

Example

T assigns a group of students to give a virtual tour around Borobudur using Google Streetview (web app). Ss pretend to be a tour guide explaining the temple and its interesting spots.

T checks Ss pronunciation, fluency, vocabulary choice, and grammar.

Speaking 2

Ss do presentation individually about a place in GMaps. The presentation takes form in a virtual tour around a place using GMaps Web app.

Example

T assigns every S to take a 360 photo of a place. The photo can be created using Streetview mobile app and the result has to be uploaded to GMaps. Ss do presentation by displaying their own 360 photo and describe the condition in that photo.

T checks Ss pronunciation, fluency, vocabulary choice, and grammar.

Tour Builder

Definition

A web app that is based on Google Maps and it allows users create a tour on particular spots in Gmaps. Anyone with Google account can use this app for free and he/she is able to create a virtual tour than can be shared via links that is distributable through email, social media, and blog.

Platform

Web app

Usage in Language Learning

T asks Ss to work individually or in pair to create a virtual tour on Google Map using Tour Builder web app. The tour can be a culinary tour, historical tour, museum tour, and many more. For example, Ss create a tour on museums in Jakarta. They have to write an introductory paragraph about the tour and write descriptive or argumentative paragraph on museums that they include in their virtual tour.

Ss have to explain the reasons of visiting the museums in the virtual tour. To make the tour interesting, ss can add photos that provide visual impression on the place they are talking about. The photos can come from ss' own source or they use the available images on Google Image or other relevant websites.

Writing

Ss work individually to create a personal tour of something using Tour Builder.

Example

T assigns ss to create a personalized virtual tour around a place or places that they know well or they are familiar with. A s chooses the places to visit and he/she writes a paragraph for each place in the virtual tour. The s decides the starting and finishing point of the virtual trip. When the tour is done, the s shares the tour by sharing its link via email to his/her class teacher.

Note

Except for Tour Builder, the rest of the apps discussed in this paper are available at Appstore and Google Playstore. For online use, the apps are accessible by anyone regardless of their computer platforms.